

Studies in Dieckmann Cyclisation. Part II. Dieckmann Cyclisation of Trimethyl 2-Methylhexane-1,2,5-Tricarboxylate

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The Dieckmann cyclisation of trimethyl 2-methylhexane-1,2,5-tricarboxylate (Ia) with sodium dust in benzene medium proceeds smoothly, but no cyclisation can be effected by sodium methoxide in methanol. The cyclisation of (Ia) is presumed to proceed through a boat form transition state intermediate, since the chair form intermediate would involve 1,3-diaxial interaction. Synthesis of the tri-ester (Ia) starting from ethyl 5-oxo-2-methylhexanoate has been described.

In Part I (Dutta and Biswas, this *Journal* 1961, 38, 335) of this series, it was postulated that the cyclisation of triethyl 2-methylpentane-1,2,5-tricarboxylate (Ib) failed to yield any six-ring cyclisation product owing to a strong 1,3-diaxial interaction between the methyl group and the group R' in the transition state intermediate (II). This would certainly involve higher energy than the five-ring intermediate involving no such interaction (Dutta and Biswas, *loc. cit.*).

(Ia: R=R'=Me; Ib: R=H; R'=Et)

(II: R'=O⁻ or OEt; R''=OEt or O⁻) (III: R=O⁻ or OMe; R'=OMe or O⁻)

With a view to testing this hypothesis, we synthesised trimethyl 2-methylhexane-1,2,5-tricarboxylate (Ia) in which the cyclisation at C₅ was prevented (*vide infra*) by a methyl group and thus leaving the alternative cyclisation only at C₁ to proceed through a highly strained transition state intermediate (III). Contrary to our expectation the cyclisation in benzene medium using sodium dust, however, proceeded smoothly. On the other hand, no cyclisation could be effected by the action of sodium methoxide in refluxing methanol, a reagent which smoothly brought about the cyclisation of the lower homologue (Ib) (Dutta and Biswas, *loc. cit.*). These results support our view that the cyclisation through the intermediate (II) or (III) involves higher energy, due to 1,3-diaxial interaction between CH₃: O⁻ (or OEt or OMe).

Recently it has been demonstrated that cyclohexane ring in certain cases exists preferentially in the boat form (Barton *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 2907; Lyle, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1957, 22, 1280; George and Wright; *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 80, 1200; Djerassi *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1959, 81, 4997). In a recent communication Allinger and Freiberg (*ibid.*, 1960, 82, 2393) have obtained evidence to show that the *trans*-isomer of 1,3-dibutyl⁶ cyclohexane exists in boat form. They found the difference in energy between the chair and boat forms to be 5.9 ± 0.6 kcal.

In the light of the above considerations we are led to postulate that in cyclisation of the tri-ester (Ia), as the transition state intermediate (IV) involving the boat form will preclude the 1,3-diaxial interaction of the type associated with (III), the reaction in all probability proceeds via (IV). This is in harmony with the reluctance of the tri-ester (Ia) to cyclisation by the action of sodium methoxide in methanol, possibly owing to the failure to attain the energy required to flip the molecule into a boat form intermediate. The intermediate (IV) on loss of the methoxyl ion is expected to yield (V). This is free to assume the chair form (VI) due to the absence of 1,3-diaxial interaction. The final step will be completed by the formation of the enolate (VII). The cyclisation should, therefore, be expected to be facile in benzene, which is able to provide the required energy for the transition state (IV) since the transformation of (V) to (VII) through (VI) will actually involve a gain in energy.

For the preparation of the tri-ester (Ia) the procedure employed for the synthesis of the lower homologue (Ib), developed by Banerjee (this *Journal*, 1940, 17, 423), was employed. Ethyl 5-oxo-2-methylhexanoate (VIII) was prepared by an improved procedure through the Michael addition (77% yield) of ethyl acetoacetate to methyl methacrylate (Meek *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 813) followed by hydrolysis and esterification of the resulting δ -keto-acid with ethanol and sulphuric acid. The keto-ester (VIII) was then allowed to react with ethyl cyanoacetate according to the procedure of Cope *et al.* (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 63, 3452) to yield the unsaturated cyano-ester (IX) in good yield. Addition of the elements of hydrogen cyanide to the unsaturated cyano-ester (Hope and Sheldon, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 121, 2223; Banerjee, *loc. cit.*) produced the saturated dicyano-ester (X) in excellent yield. The latter on hydrolysis with concentrated hydrochloric acid

furnished a crystalline tri-acid (XI), which was esterified with methanol and sulphuric acid to yield the desired tri-ester (Ia),

(X: R=R₂=Et; R₁=R₃=CN)

(XI: R=R₂=R₃=H; R₁=CO₂H)

(XII a: R₁=CO₂Me;

R₂=H; R₃=Me;

XII b: R₂=CO₂Me;

R₁=H; R₃=Me)

(XIII: R=R₁=R₂=H; R₃=Me)

(XVI: R=Et; R₂=CO₂Et; R₁=R₃=H)

(XVII: R=Me; R₁=R₂=R₃=H)

(XIV: R=R'=H)

(XV: R=CO₂Me; R'=Me)

The β -keto-ester, obtained by the cyclisation of (Ia), was hydrolysed to a keto-acid (XIII). This yielded a D.N.P.H. derivative, which showed no depression on admixture with the same derivative of a keto acid obtained from another sequence of reactions starting from methyl 1-methylcyclohexan-3-one-1-carboxylate.

The compound (XVI) was obtained through the pyrolysis of the ethoxyoxalyl ester obtained by the condensation of diethyl oxalate (Kotz, *Annalen*, 1906; 350, 210; 358, 198) with methyl 1-methylcyclohexan-3-one-carboxylate (XVII) in presence of ethanolic sodium ethoxide. An attempt to prepare the compound by condensation of diethyl carbonate with (XVII) produced an enolic ether (cf. Wallingford, *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 63, 2252).

The structure of the β -keto-ester, thus obtained, was proved through methylation in benzene solution. The methylated product on hydrolysis gave a keto acid which could not be induced to crystallise. The D. N. P. H. derivative showed no depression on admixture with the D.N.P.H. derivative of the keto-acid (XIII) obtained before.

In this connection the methylation of the β -keto-ester obtained by the Dieckmann cyclisation of ethyl 2-methylpentane-1, 2,5-tricarboxylate (Ib) (Dutta and Biswas, *loc. cit.*; Banerjee, *loc. cit.*) was studied. The product on hydrolysis gave an acid which was isomeric with (XIII) and should be represented as (XIV). This yielded a semicarbazone, m.p. 186-87° (decomp.). No D.N.P.H. derivative could be obtained. This showed that the product from that obtained by the cyclisation of (Ia) had a structure different from (XV), which might have been formed if the cyclisation of (Ia) proceeded appreciably at C₂.

Moreover, the cyclisation product of (Ia) developed an intense violet coloration with alcoholic ferric chloride solution, indicating the structure of the β -keto-ester to be (XIIa) and not (XIIb), which was corroborated by other reactions to be communicated later.

EXPERIMENTAL

Ethyl 5-oxo-2-methylhexanoate (VIII). To a solution of sodium ethoxide in ethanol (from 0.8 g sodium and 25 c.c. anhydrous ethanol) was added dropwise freshly distilled ethyl acetoacetate (50 c.c.) while the reaction flask was being cooled in iced water. A solution of freshly distilled methyl α -methylacrylate (27.5 g) in dry benzene (30 c.c.) was added dropwise to the above product with constant swirling. After half-an-hour the solution was heated under reflux on a water bath for 5 hours and then left at room temperature for 48 hours. The reaction mixture was acidified with cold dilute acetic acid and extracted twice with ether-benzene mixture. The combined ether-benzene layer was washed thoroughly free of acid. After removal of the solvent the residue on distillation gave methyl 4-ethoxycarbonyl 5-oxo-2-methylhexanoate (49.1 g), b.p. 130-32°/4.5 mm (lit. b.p. 103-105°/0.5 mm) as a pale, yellowish green oil in 77% yield (Meek *et al. loc. cit.* report 57%).

The above ester was heated under reflux with 6*N* HCl (150 c.c.) for 20 hours. The brown solution was evaporated in a porcelain basin on a steam bath as far as practicable. After removal of last traces of moisture by azeotropic distillation with benzene, the residual brown gummy acid was heated under reflux with a mixture of ethanol (twice distilled over CaO: 60 c.c.) and H₂SO₄ (conc., 3.6 c.c.), on a steam bath for 18 hours to furnish the ester (27.5 g), b.p. 84-85°/2 mm. (Found: C, 63.01; H, 9.08. C₉H₁₆O₃ requires C, 62.79; H, 9.30%).

1,5-Dicarbethoxy-1-cyano-2-methylhexane-1 (IX).—A solution of the above keto-ester (27.5 g), ethyl cyanoacetate (18.7 g) and glacial acetic acid (8 c.c.) in benzene (60 c.c.) was continuously distilled with addition of ammonium acetate (3.5 g) using a constant water separator. Water was removed from time to time and the distillation was continued for 2 hours more after the separation of water became negligible. After a total period of 16 hours, the reaction mixture was cooled and washed thoroughly with ice-cold water to free from acid. After evaporation of the solvent the residue on distillation furnished the unsaturated cyano-ester (36.5 g), b.p. 156-58°/2.5 mm, $n_D^{26.5}$ 1.4684. (Found: C, 63.51; H, 7.80. C₁₄H₂₁O₄N requires C, 62.90; H, 7.90%).

1,5-Dicarbethoxy-1,2-dicyano-2-methylhexane (X).—A solution of potassium cyanide (19 g) in water (103 c.c.) was slowly added to a solution of the above unsaturated cyano-ester (36.5 g) in rectified spirit (158 c.c.). The mixture was cooled in ice for 30 mins. and treated dropwise with HCl (d. 1.155, 23.5 c.c.) diluted with ice-cold water (16 c.c.). It was then acidified with HCl (23.5 c.c. acid diluted with 23.5 c.c. water). The dicyano-ester, which separated as a thick oil, was taken up in ether. The ethereal extract was washed with water, dried (Na₂SO₄), solvent removed. The residue was distilled to furnish a colorless oil (35.2 g) b.p. 182-84°/0.8 mm. n_D^{27} 1.4512. (Found: C, 61.89; H, 7.68. C₁₅H₂₂O₄N₂ requires C, 61.21; H, 7.53%).

2-Methylhexane-1,2,5-tricarboxylic Acid (XI).—A mixture of the above dicyano-diester (34.3 g) and HCl (conc. 350 c.c.) was heated under reflux for 96 hours. The reaction mixture was evaporated in a porcelain basin on a steam bath. The solid residue was crystallised from ether-petroleum ether (40°-60°) mixture to furnish a white crystalline solid, m.p. 149-48.5 (Found: C, 51.57; H, 6.70. C₁₀H₁₆O₆ requires C, 51.72; H, 6.93%).

Trimethyl-2-methylhexane-1,2,5-tricarboxylate (Ia).—The above crude acid (25 g.) was esterified by heating with a mixture of anhydrous methanol (150 c.c.) and H_2SO_4 (d 1.84; 21 c.c.) under reflux for 90 hours and worked up in an usual manner using ether-benzene mixture for extraction to furnish the tri-ester (23.3 g), b.p. 129-30°/0.5 mm. n_D^{25} 1.4462. (Found: C, 57.05; H, 7.76. $C_{13}H_{22}O_6$ requires C, 56.92; H, 8.08%).

Dieckmann Cyclisation of Trimethyl 2-Methylhexane-1,2,5-tricarboxylate (Ia)

(a) *With Sodium Dust in Benzene Solution.*—A mixture of the tri-ester (4.38 g) and sodium dust (0.76 g) in dry benzene (15 c.c.) and anhydrous methanol (0.1 c.c.) was heated under reflux (oil bath, 105-10°) in an atmosphere of nitrogen for 3½ hours. The brownish reaction mixture was cooled, acidified with ice-cold dilute hydrochloric acid. The benzene layer was separated and the aqueous layer extracted thrice with ether. The combined ether-benzene layer was washed with brine and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. After removal of the solvent the residual oil was distilled to furnish the β -keto-ester (2.9 g) b.p. 100-105°/0.5 mm. It gave an intense violet coloration with ethanolic ferric chloride solution. (Found: C, 59.36; H, 7.58. $C_{12}H_{18}O_5$ requires C, 59.50; H, 7.43%).

Hydrolysis of the β -Keto-ester to Keto-acid (XIII).—The above β -keto-ester (2.9 g) was heated under reflux with a mixture of 20% HCl (28 c.c.) and glacial acetic acid (14 c.c.) for 24 hours. The volatile solvent was removed under reduced pressure (water pump) from oil bath at 130-40°. After removal of the last traces of moisture by dry benzene, the residue when evaporatively distilled at 100-10°/0.5 mm gave a distillate (1.4 g) as a colourless gummy liquid, n_D^{27} 1.4745. (Found: C, 63.35; H, 8.17. $C_9H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 63.53; H, 8.23%).

The 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone was prepared by the perchloric acid method and recrystallised from benzene, m.p. 183-84°. (Found: N, 15.55. $C_{15}H_{18}N_4O_6$ requires N, 16.00%).

(b) *With Sodium Methoxide in Methanol Solution.*—A mixture of the tri-ester (4.38 g) and methanolic sodium methoxide solution (prepared from 0.41 g. sodium and 15 c.c. Mg-dry methanol) was heated under reflux (oil bath, 90-95°) in an atmosphere of nitrogen for 3½ hours. The brownish reaction mixture was cooled, acidified with ice-cold HCl (dil), diluted with ice-cold water, and extracted thrice with ether. The combined ethereal extract was washed with brine and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. After removal of the solvent the residual oil was distilled to furnish a distillate (2.86 g), b.p. 110-116°/0.2 mm. The distillate did not give any coloration with ethanolic ferric chloride solution.

2,5-Dimethylcyclopentanone-2-acetic Acid (XIV).—To a suspension of powdered sodium (0.76 g) in dry thiophene-free benzene (25 c.c.) the tri-ester (Ib, 5.06 g) was added and the mixture was heated under reflux (oil bath, 95-100°) for 3½ hours. The reaction mixture was cooled in ice for one hour and methyl iodide (3 c.c.) was added with shaking and left overnight. Next day more methyl iodide (3 c.c.) was added and heated under reflux on a steam bath for 4 hours. To the cooled reaction mixture water was added and the benzene layer was separated. The aqueous layer was extracted with ether. The combined ether-benzene layer was washed with water. After removal of the solvent the residue was heated under reflux with 20% HCl (35 c.c.) for 60 hours. The reaction mixture was cooled and thoroughly extracted with ether after saturation with sodium chloride. The combined ethereal extract was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. After removal of the solvent the residue on evaporative distillation at 100-10°/0.4 mm gave a distillate (1.4 g) as a colourless thick liquid, $n_D^{29.5}$ 1.4631. (Found: C, 63.11; H, 8.28. $C_9H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 63.53; H, 8.23%).

The *semicarbazone* was prepared by the sodium acetate method and recrystallised from aqueous methanol, m.p. 186-87° (decomp.) (Found: C, 52.91; H, 7.57. $C_{10}H_{17}O_3N_3$ requires C, 52.86; H, 7.48%).

Diethyl 1-Methylcyclohexan-3-one-1,4-dicarboxylate (XVI).—To a solution of sodium ethoxide (prepared from 0.55 g. sodium and 7.2 c.c. anhydrous ethanol), cooled in freezing mixture, was added a well-cooled mixture of methyl 1-methylcyclohexan-3-one-1-carboxylate (3.7 g) and diethyl oxalate (3.5 g); the mixture was shaken for half-an-hour and left overnight. Next day ice-cold water (80 c.c.) was added, acidified with ice-cold H_2SO_4 (1:50), and extracted with benzene. The extract was washed with water till free of acid. After removal of the solvent the residue was heated on oil bath at 180-90° with the addition of glass powder for half-an-hour and then distilled to furnish the di-ester (3.9 g), b.p. 126-28/1.5 mm. The di-ester developed an intense violet colour with EtOH- $FeCl_3$. Analysis indicated that it was a diethyl ester. (Found: C, 60.77; H, 7.40. $C_{13}H_{20}O_5$ requires C, 60.93; H, 7.81%).

1,4-Dimethyl-cyclohexan-3-one-1-carboxylic Acid (XIII).—To a suspension of sodium dust (0.28 g) in dry thiophene-free benzene (20 c.c.) was added dropwise a solution of the β -ketoester (VI, 2.6 g) in dry thiophene-free benzene (25 c.c.) and left overnight. Next day the reaction mixture was heated to reflux on a steam-bath for 1 hour; the reaction mixture was cooled in an ice-salt bath, treated with methyl iodide (1.5 c.c.) with shaking, and left overnight at room temperature. Next day after the addition of a further quantity of methyl iodide (1.5 c.c.) it was heated to reflux for 4 hours. The cooled reaction mixture was poured into iced water; the benzene layer was separated; the aqueous layer was extracted once with ether-benzene mixture and added to the benzene layer. The combined ether-benzene extract was washed with ice-cold 5% NaOH solution, and then with water to free it of alkali. After removal of the solvent the residue was heated under reflux with a mixture of 20% HCl (24 c.c.) and glacial acetic acid (15 c.c.). The volatile solvent was removed under reduced pressure (water pump) from oil bath at 130-40°. After removal of the last traces of moisture by dry benzene, the residue, when evaporatively distilled at 95-100°C/0.4 mm, gave a distillate (1 g) as a colourless gummy liquid, $n_D^{27.5}$ 1.4743. (Found: C, 63.55; H, 7.92. $C_9H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 63.53; H, 8.23%).

The 2, 4-*dinitrophenylhydrazone* was prepared by the perchloric acid method (Neuberg, *et al.*, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1952, 7, 238) and recrystallised from benzene, m.p. 183-84°. No depression in m.p. was observed when mixed with the D. N. P. H. of 1,4-dimethylcyclohexan-3-one-1-carboxylic acid obtained through another sequence of reactions (Dutta and Biswas, *loc. cit.*)

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